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Shaping the Ground

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Mapping the fruit tree biodiversity of transitioning landscapes

liminal_{shape} rural futures

Index

1.1 Summary of the Action-Research	2
2.1 Challenge Results	3
2.2 Contextual Overview The reasons for tree mapping in the context of Monti Prenestini	4
2.3 Methodological Approach	6
2.4 Challenges and Limitations	9
2.5 Conclusions	10
3.1 Index of Appendices	12

1.1 Summary of the action-research¹

Shaping the Ground was an experimental research initiative conducted in Monti Prenestini with the aim of developing an effective and accessible method for mapping tree resources in marginal territories, as a first concrete step towards the launch of the *territorial laboratory*² proposed under the *Transitioning a Landscape*³ project.

The Challenge was focused on the construction and field testing of a participatory survey method capable of returning a spatial reading of the tree biodiversity present in transitional agricultural landscapes. The method was developed and tested through four successive phases, involving moments of theoretical discussion, tool design, dialogue with farmers and local associations, mapping activities in a pilot area, and reporting and closing reflections.

Three main operational tools were developed: a model specification sheet for describing fruit tree varieties and cultivars, a digital mapping module that can be used via smartphone, and a summary of tree cultivation techniques. Their effectiveness was tested in a sample area of 9.3 hectares, spread over several plots belonging to three local farmers. The mapping allowed the method to be tested in heterogeneous environmental situations and to improve its usability and consistency with regional standards.

In addition to the toolkit and the first experimental database produced, the project included a landscape enhancement exercise led by Landscape First⁴, which enabled reflection on the role of fruit trees in the perception and accessibility of the agricultural landscape. *Shaping the Ground* provided much of the operational, spatial, and agronomic knowledge needed to initiate the experiments of the *territorial laboratory*, while at the same time laying the groundwork for replicating this process in other areas facing similar challenges.

¹ Lewin, Kurt. "Action Research and Minority Problems." *Journal of Social Issues* 2 (1946): 34-46.

² The territorial lab is an applied research tool conceived during *Transitioning a Landscape*, halfway between *Living Labs* and *Land-Based Labs*. It is a place dedicated to experimentation oriented toward landscape protection and regeneration of depopulated areas, with the aim of bringing out new forms of social innovation and stimulating the economic fabric. Participatory ways of solving concrete problems through innovative approaches makes new potentials tangible and motivates the investments needed to initiate larger-scale transformations.

³ Read more in the *Transitioning a Landscape*, 2024 initiative report.

⁴ Landscape First (<https://www.landscapefirst.com/>) is a publishing and cultural platform dedicated to promoting contemporary landscape architecture, led by landscape architect Gaël Glauzel.

2.1

Challenge Results

The *Shaping the Ground* project produced three main outcomes. The first was the creation of a toolkit for fruit tree mapping, designed to facilitate data collection in an accessible, participatory and structured way. The toolkit includes three main components: a summary of tree cultivation techniques, a digital form that can be used via smartphone to collect information on individual tree specimens in the field, and a specification sheet for describing fruit tree cultivars. These tools enable survey participants to gain basic knowledge about arboriculture, facilitate accurate mapping that integrates georeferenced data and images for each specimen, and allow for later identification of the presence and prevalence of specific cultivars in the area. They also organize all the data needed to assess the technical characteristics, cultivation requirements and production potential of each recorded species and corresponding cultivars, laying the foundation for future spatial analysis and stewardship strategies.

Fig. 1

Map showing all plots mapped during the Challenge, classified according to their current use. See attachments for high-resolution versions of all maps produced.

The second outcome was the practical testing of the toolkit in Monti Prenestini, applied to a sample area consisting of land from three landowners who actively participated in the research. Although the parcels were within the same district, they were discontinuous and had different conditions, allowing us to test the mapping on a variety of use-types: from age-old chestnut groves to dry grasslands in different management states, including grazed, hayed, or in early natural successional processes. The approach taken was that of an integral mapping, recording data for all identifiable fruit trees in the selected

parcels. This work covered a total of 9.3 hectares, documenting 542 trees belonging to 19 different species and numerous cultivars. The data collected was subsequently organized in a database and visualized through maps that represented the prevalence and spatial distribution of the trees, highlighting the specific characteristics of the different plot types and allowing us to hypothesize the different historical periods of planting that characterize the landscape. This experimental phase also allowed the toolkit to be improved, adapting it to the conditions encountered in the field and further clarifying its potential for future applications.

The third outcome was a practical exercise to study and enhance some of the surveyed tree specimens, carried out under the guidance of Landscape First. This activity aimed to explore the effort required to recover existing trees at the margins of fields or on parcels undergoing natural succession, where invasive vegetation, such as brambles, tends to smother plants. Participants freed some specimens from surrounding vegetation and observed the different impacts that neglect and caretaking exert on the character of the agricultural landscape of Monti Prenestini. This intervention revealed not only the challenges associated with large-scale restoration of tree heritage elements, but also their aesthetic and cultural potential, especially when made more visible and accessible. The activity suggested new possibilities for integrating these features of the landscape into hiking itineraries and new land-use strategies. At the same time, it has raised questions about the need to balance the recovery of traditional landscape elements, such as rows along field edges, with the creation of new, more functional tree configurations. Striking a balance between conservation and innovation is key to gaining traction in these landscapes—stewarding the differentiating features that exist, while guiding their evolution over time toward forms that respond to pragmatic contemporary necessities.

2.2

Contextual Overview

The reasons for tree mapping in the context of Monti Prenestini

2.2.1 A First Step Toward Creating a *Territorial Laboratory*

The *Shaping the Ground* project is inserted as the first concrete activation of the project for a *territorial laboratory*, developed at the end of the *Transitioning a Landscape* initiative. This Challenge, carried out in Monti Prenestini in 2024, had explored the phenomenon of agricultural abandonment and the consequent transformation of the Monti Prenestini landscape in the last century, highlighting the progressive loss of arid prairies and the spread of a narrative of "inevitable naturalization" of the territory. In response to this vision, the team had proposed the creation of a long-term laboratory aimed at exploring new forms of productive stewardship through participatory experimentation on sample areas of Monti Prenestini. The idea was to activate a first pilot area, able to act as a beacon on the territory: a place to make new potentials and alternative models of landscape

management visible, counteracting the passivity that often accompanies the dynamics of abandonment.

In order to propose a new way of looking at the progressively neglected landscape, the plan drawn up by the team was to articulate experimentation along three types of terrain along the current ecological gradient: arid prairies, transition zones and forested areas. Each environmental strip offered specific opportunities and critical issues, requiring differentiated but coordinated approaches. Within this framework, the *Shaping the Ground* challenge was designed to have a dual function: on the one hand, to develop a method for learning about and mapping the existing tree stock; on the other hand, to begin an initial round of field experimentation.

2.2.2 Rationale for Emphasis on Fruit Tree Species

Within this framework, the choice to start with arboriculture was not accidental. The team considered it strategic to focus on this component first for several reasons. First, it is a type of intervention that needs to be started right away because of the long time required to produce tangible results. Second, arboriculture lends itself to less intensive management than other production systems such as livestock farming, making it suitable as a starting point for the *territorial laboratory* due to its limited complexity. Finally, it presents itself as a complementary sector to other efforts already present in the area: while initiatives related to the enhancement of meats, cheeses and chestnuts are already active, the variety of other local fruit trees is still less recognized, both culturally and economically. Working on this heritage therefore offers an opportunity to expand the area's gastronomic offerings, helping to build a broader and more articulated culinary identity capable of distinguishing Monti Prenestini from other territories in the region.

From this perspective, the Challenge was conceived as a preparatory act to actual experimentation. Before actively intervening in the landscape, it is necessary to know it thoroughly. *Shaping the Ground* therefore set out to develop a scalable and accessible method for mapping tree biodiversity and its distribution in underappreciated territories, starting with Monti Prenestini but with the ambition of building a replicable toolkit in similar contexts. The focus was not only on the development of technical tools, but also on the possibility of integrating this knowledge with the enhancement policies already active at the regional level, in particular with the Voluntary Regional Register of Plant Genetic Resources (RVR) promoted by ARSIAL.⁵

This institutional linkage is an integral part of the *territorial laboratory* approach: knowing and documenting the tree heritage is only the first step. The *territorial laboratory* plans to focus on experimentation with land-based management, but also to trigger broader stewardship mechanisms capable of benefiting not only the sample area, but the entire territory. The possibility of initiating pathways for official recognition of cultivars, activating incentives for those who protect them, and building a collective narrative around the productive landscape are key elements in transforming individual local actions into systemic regeneration strategies. In this sense, *Shaping the Ground*

⁵ The Voluntary Regional Registry of Plant Genetic Resources (RVR) is a tool of the Lazio Region, managed by ARSIAL (Agenzia Regionale per lo Sviluppo e l'Innovazione dell'Agricoltura del Lazio), aimed at protecting and enhancing local varieties of agronomic, food and cultural interest through their identification, conservation and official recognition.

represents not only a technical or operational challenge, but an initial building block in the construction of a new territorial infrastructure, based on knowledge, collaboration, and the cultural and productive value of existing food biodiversity.

2.2.3 Tree Biodiversity: A Lever for Marginal Territories

The agrarian landscape of the Prenestini Mountains, like many mid-mountain territories⁶ in Italy, is characterized by a widespread but fragmented tree biodiversity, which survives today on field margins, in family gardens or abandoned plots. Many of these varieties—such as dwarf pears, ancient apple trees, walnut trees, or wild species like hawthorn and blackthorn, are present on the territory without being systematically catalogued or stewarded. In this context, local non-profit organizations such as Viviamo Rocca di Cave APS⁷ or national organizations like Slow Food⁸ play an important role in contributing to the cultural and institutional protection and enhancement of these resources, despite the absence of a shared territorial strategy.

However, these varieties represent much more than a botanical curiosity: they are a strategic starting point for imagining new development models in territories that today suffer from economic marginality, logistical isolation and demographic decline. In these contexts, where integration with industrial agricultural supply chains is structurally limited, the stewardship of local specificities can offer an alternative competitive advantage based on differentiation and historical narratives.

In particular, traditional arboriculture can be a concrete lever for reactivating local economies in areas where the availability of labor is limited and discontinuous. Unlike other labor-intensive agricultural activities, fruit tree care – while requiring specific skills – is characterized by a seasonal and punctual management of most of the human capital. This makes it compatible with part-time labor engagements that can be structured through temporary presence on the territory where not locally available. In a scenario of depopulation and low attractiveness for new residents, this characteristic can make arboriculture a key element in the start of territorial regeneration processes. In marginal territories, there is often a lack of planning and catalytic financial resources. That said, once these are identified, limited human capital becomes one of the greatest barriers to the success of new enterprises of all scales.

Identifying, documenting and making this biodiversity visible is thus an essential step in activating niche stewardship paths capable of combining tradition and innovation. It is not a matter of replicating models of the past, but of reading the productive potential of the area in the light of its historical traces, and transforming them into the basis for modern food systems, consistent with contemporary agricultural techniques and the needs of today's markets. In this sense, tree biodiversity is not just a heritage to be protected,

⁶ Mauro Varotto, *Middle Mountains. A new geography*, Piccola Biblioteca Einaudi. Maps, Einaudi, Turin, 2020.

⁷ Viviamo Rocca di Cave APS is actively involved in a process to develop recognition for a local walnut cultivar in Rocca di Cave and played a key role in facilitating a meeting with ARSIAL representatives, introducing the group to the Voluntary Regional Registry (RVR) program for the protection of local plant genetic resources.

⁸ Monti Prenestini counts on three Slow Food Presidiums.

but a cultural and genetic infrastructure on which to build identity, reputation, know-how and new economies.

2.3

Methodological Approach

The *Shaping the Ground* project consisted of four operational phases, alternating between remote work and field activities. The methodological approach combined theoretical discussion, practical tool development, territorial exploration and landscape experimentation, with the aim of building a flexible but effective method for mapping tree resources in Monti Prenestini. Each phase was designed to respond to context-specific needs, enhancing available resources and ensuring consistency with the long-term goals of the project.

2.3.1 Phase 1: Project Design and Tool Development

The first phase took place online and had a twofold function: to build a shared theoretical framework and to initiate the development of operational tools. Participants were able to discuss the goals of the initiative, imagining possible trajectories of evolution of the mapping method that was being built. Discussions focused in particular on the possibility of creating tools capable of producing an in-depth knowledge of the fruit trees present in the territory and of strengthening active agricultural protection, relating them to already existing regulatory devices such as the Regional Voluntary Registry of Plant Genetic Resources (RVR). Promoted by ARSIAL, the RVR protects the food heritage of Lazio ex-situ and in-situ. Within this process, a first core of the toolkit was developed, consisting of a summary of tree cultivation techniques (designed to allow mapping in a participatory way, including people without specialized knowledge), a specification sheet for the description of species and cultivars, and a digital form for the registration of specimens identified in the field via smartphone using Jotform. The design was conducted taking into account the data collection criteria required by agencies such as ARSIAL, to ensure their eventual interoperability and contribution to institutional recognition of potentially protectable varieties and subsequent economic support to farmers conserving in-situ populations. The collection of different image types for each individual specimen was considered essential in order to create a database through which trees could be sorted to identify institutionally protected cultivars or specimens of special reproductive interest using image recognition software.

2.3.2 Phase 2: Practical Experimentation of Mapping Toolkit

The second phase took place in Monti Prenestini and was dedicated to testing the functionality of the mapping toolkit. The area selected for experimentation extended between the localities of Cigliano, Valle Marzana and Piano Saliato, within the municipalities of Castel San Pietro Romano, Capranica Prenestina and Rocca di Cave. This choice was based on the density of active farms, the coexistence of different forms of land stewardship and agricultural

abandonment, and the possibility of continuity with the Reviving Trails project, which had already identified the area's potential for a loop route capable of giving greater visibility to the area's limited but diverse traditional productive landscape. The chosen location also allowed Liminal to expand its direct relationships with local farmers, a key issue for further activities already envisioned during *Transitioning a Landscape*.

The mapping focused on plots made available by three local farmers, which provided access to multiple discontinuous plots of land, each characterized by different uses: old chestnut groves, mowed prairies, animal pastures, mixed orchards, gardens, and fallow land. This selection criterion – based on land ownership – made it possible, on the one hand, to obtain consent for the activities, and on the other, to work on units that, despite their fragmentation, realistically reflect the agricultural organization of the land and the different types of distribution of fruit trees.

Field activities began with a meeting with representatives of ARSIAL, Viviamo Rocca di Cave APS and several farmers, aimed at establishing an initial operational contact with some of the actors currently involved in the protection of the area's tree genetic resources. An introductory walk with one of the collaborating farmers took place on the following day, during which the tree species – both cultivated and wild – that make up the agricultural landscape of the area were recognized and discussed. On this basis, an initial mapping test was carried out in a sample area, at the end of which modifications were made to the digital form and the data collection criteria were refined, making the system more suitable for the conditions detected in the field. Next, participants divided into groups and integrally mapped every fruit tree within the participating farmers' plots. The decision to adopt an integral rather than selective approach due to the need to return a complete and comparable picture of the tree distribution, which could allow us to draw conclusions about the history of use and the degree of maintenance of each plot.

2.3.3 Phase 3: Landscape Experiment with Landscape First

As a result of the mapping, the importance of field margins as sites of significant but often overlooked tree presence became clear. Some specimens were the result of spontaneous propagation, others remnants of earlier plantings that had a complementary function to the prevailing historical land use for grazing. Landscape First proposed to focus a hands-on intervention on this invisible heritage, with the aim of assessing its status, the effort required for eventual restoration, and the effect that such enhancement may have on the perception of the landscape by those crossing local trails.

The intervention took place in a plot used as a hayfield, where four points with different conditions of neglect were selected: a row of wild hazel trees, an ancient pear tree, and two large walnut trees. At each of these points, action was taken to clear the trees of weeds, observing in real time the perceptual change in the landscape. The objective was not only to verify the technical feasibility of the recovery, but also to explore the cultural and visual implications that greater care of the margins can generate in the perception of an agrarian landscape, in which the protection of existing resources appears to be a necessary step in any territorial regeneration strategy, whether touristic or productive.

Fig. 2

Example of the Jotform form developed for field data collection.

15:10 5G

< Specimen Submission Form,...

Specimen Submission Form

Shaping the Ground Challenge

Surveyors

- Natasha Balwit
- Justin Balwit Cheung
- Dipon Bose
- Nicolás Delgado Alcega
- Gael Glaudel
- Alessandro Gori
- Maren Johnson
- Lindsay Lebel
- Silvia Pennisi
- Leonardo Tripelli
- Other

Jotform Create your own Jotform

2.3.4 Phase 4: Data Processing, Methodological Refinement and Reporting

The fourth and final phase again took place online and was aimed at systematizing the work performed. In this phase, the data collected was processed in a georeferenced database and visualized through a series of maps capable of representing the distribution, density and characteristics of the species observed during the experimental phase of the mapping method. In parallel, the group reflected on the effectiveness of the method, making revisions to the toolkit, imagining other application contexts, and discussing the future opportunities offered by a participatory tree heritage mapping approach.

2.4

Challenges and Limitations

Field activities took place under conditions that were not always favorable, highlighting several critical operational issues. Comprehensive field mapping required intensive exploratory work on soils that were often uneven, with tall grass and an extensive presence of brambles and weeds along field edges. It is precisely these edges – where a significant portion of the tree stock is

concentrated that proved to be among the most difficult areas to systematically explore and document every fruit tree.

From a technical point of view, there was a generalized difficulty in recognizing some varieties accurately, particularly when dealing with wild species or hybridized specimens. Participants were able to develop some familiarity with the main species, but the distinction between cultivated and wild varieties remained a partial limitation to the completeness of data collection, often requiring support from farmers or photographic comparison of the database at a later stage. In addition, there was a tendency in some cases, when doing comprehensive plot mapping, to spend large amounts of time mapping wild trees of little genetic or productive relevance, opening up a consideration of how to integrate more effective selection criteria without sacrificing methodological rigor.

An additional critical issue concerned the uploading of collected data. The total absence of internet connection in so many of the mapped areas limited the ability to upload data to the digital form in real time. Not only did this significantly slow down the mapping, but some participants experienced problems during the subsequent loading of the forms using Jotform. Several photographs were lost at this stage, without it being possible to determine with certainty the causes of this malfunction, which affected only some devices and not others.

The toolkit developed during the first phase demonstrated good overall effectiveness, but some of its components proved in need of revision once applied in the field. The digital form, initially designed for smooth and intuitive use, proved less efficient in the absence of a stable connection. Ongoing revision of the form – like the addition of more image requirements and the simplification of some descriptive sections – improved data collection, but also highlighted the need to think about offline or paper versions in case of prolonged use in remote territories. Similarly, the specification sheet, which is useful for organizing information on cultivars, showed limitations in distinguishing between information that can be easily collected in the field and that which needs in-depth agronomic or historical investigation.

2.5

Conclusions

The Shaping the Ground project made it possible to test an initial method of participatory mapping of tree resources in Monti Prenestini, with the aim of learning more about the area and starting an experimental pathway related to productive landscape protection. The active participation of farmers and local associations proved essential to obtain meaningful data and guide the work based on the knowledge already present in the area. However, the difference between the two main approaches adopted became clear: on the one hand,

systematic mapping provided a useful reading of the morphology of the landscape and the distribution of fruit trees; on the other hand, dialogue with local actors proved more effective in identifying specific varieties and cultivars, accessing tacit knowledge, and identifying relevant specimens.

This distinction made it possible to clarify the limitations and potential of the proposed method. Mapping has proven to be particularly useful as a spatial diagnostic tool: it makes it possible to distinguish the different generations of planting and management that characterize plots, supports comparisons with other mapping sources, and helps to read changes over time. In addition, it provides an information infrastructure for possible institutional stewardship pathways, for example in the case of public subsidy requests by individual farmers for the protection of specimens belonging to varieties already recognized by ARSIAL.

Based on these results, the method can be applied in a targeted way in other areas, including at the request of local stakeholders. One example is Viviamo Rocca di Cave, which is currently engaged in a census of the presence of walnut trees in the area, with the aim of strengthening an application to the Voluntary Regional Register (RVR). The methodology developed could help make the work of identifying single specimens on private property more efficient and produce outputs in line with ARSIAL's scientific expectations.

The experiment led by Landscape First also highlighted the different levels of commitment required to restore existing specimens. Hence the need to differentiate between interventions on the establishment of new systems – more functional and scalable – and selective interventions on old trees, to be enhanced at specific points along cultural, hiking or educational routes. This differentiation allows a more targeted use of available resources and strengthens the coherence between agricultural production and territorial identity.

Overall, the project represented a concrete step toward launching the *territorial laboratory* envisioned during *Transitioning a Landscape*. Working on the tree heritage enabled the acquisition of operational and spatial knowledge that will be fundamental for future experimentation. The methodology developed may evolve further, but it has already demonstrated that it can support a process of reading, activating and enhancing the landscape, which is necessary to implement the objectives of the *territorial laboratory*.

3.1

Index of Appendices

3.1.1 Calendar of Activities

3.1.2 Impact Framework

3.1.3 Executive Summary of Arboricultural Cultivation Techniques

3.1.4 Specimen Submission Form Parameters

3.1.5 Model Genetic Resource Specification Sheet

3.1.6 Maps of plots subject to experimental mapping

3.1.6.1. Coverage Area

3.1.6.2. Fruit Tree Species

3.1.6.3. Management Index

3.1.7 Cartographic database of experimental mapping (GeoPackage)

3.1.8 Fruit and Nut Tree Distribution Visualizations
